

The Library of Nawab Nazim of Murshidabad: Some Observations on Sir Jadunath Sarkar's Report

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The paper is a rejoinder to the *Report* submitted by Sir Jadunath Sarkar on the Library of Nawab Nazim of Murshidabad. Comments on the 'Collection' and the 'Catalogue' of the Library.

0 INTRODUCTION

Analysis of the past history always helps to assess the present situation, which in turn would take us on the right course to the bright future of any particular field of endeavour. Library and information science is no exception to this. The discipline with its dynamic nature is in quest of new horizons world over including India. The Indian library world has recognised for long a continuous need to study Indian Librarianship and library science. No study of a discipline is complete without studying its historical developments. Thus, to understand the development of librarianship in India, it is necessary to take into account the history of libraries in India. As Raman Nair [2, p.5] correctly mentioned that "Library history should enable those in the field to respect the antiquity of our calling, to appreciate the gradual advance and sometimes decline of various movements and systems and to base our future on sound foundations. We can take advantage of past experience and learn from the mistakes of others instead of repeating them. "For an understanding of the history of libraries in India one must understand the nature of existing resources available in various languages and formats. These resources were housed in palace/court libraries, temple/mosque libraries, centres of learning libraries and private libraries spread all over the country throughout centuries.

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The history of Medieval India (1206-1757) was characterised by the predominant position of the Muslim rulers. This position enabled the Muslims to import many cultural and literary activities: writing history, maintaining a record of minute details, maintaining libraries, manufacturing paper, tanning leather for book binding, employing professional binders, calligraphers to make copies, proof readers, and others. The coming of Mughals in India initiated a notable step in the progress of library development. They were well read and have been rightly called highly cultured men. The period from Babur to Aurangzeb, the Mughal emperors, runs a continuous library tradition and patronage of libraries along with other cultural and literary activities. Following the path of their emperors, the Mughal provincial governors or *Nazims* themselves made a history in the development and patronage of libraries and librarianship. Notable among them were the Nazims of Bihar, Oudh (now Ayodhya), Jaunpur, Khandesh, etc.

History of the Nawabs of Murshidabad in Bengal during the Mughal period is characterised by events which later shaped the destiny of the province in particular as well as that of the nation in general. Among the Nawabs of Bengal (also called *Nazim*) those who left their marks on the pre-Plassey history of the region are Murshid Quli Khan (1700-1727), Shuja-ud-din Muhammad Khan (1727-1739), Alibardi Khan (1740-1756) and Siraz-ud-daulah (1756-1757). But, there is very little evidence to suggest that they had any role in subjects such as the development of libraries in the kingdom. Though it is supposed that there was a big Islamic collection in the famous Katra Mosque (1723) during the reign of Murshid Quli Khan, but no trace of the same has yet been discovered. It was Nawab Nazim Humayun Jah (1824-1838) who had the credit of building a library in the Hazarduari Palace (built 1829-1837) premises only after the Dewani came under the East India Company's protection in the year 1763.

1 SIR JADUNATH SARKAR'S REPORT

Sir Jadunath Sarkar (1870-1958), an eminent scholar and historian of great repute, paid two visits to the Library of Nawab Nazim of Murshidabad in the year 1954 in company with Prof Nirod Baran Roy with a view to bringing its valuable Persian collection into light. In this connection it may be worthwhile to mention the historical fact that Sir Sarkar had the unique distinction of being the first honorary librarian of the Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi in 1916. According to Taher and Davis [4 p 15], Jadunath Sarkar is one of those few historians who have largely contributed on history of libraries in India. Thus, it could be safely presumed that his observations on the Nawab's Library were not that of a layman. What follows is a structured presentation of the *Report* on the Library which Sir Jadunath Sarkar published in the July-December 1966 issue of the *Bengal Past and Present* (hereafter referred to as the Report)[3] and some further observations on the same.

1.1 THE COLLECTION

Description of the collection could be found in the *Report* with some valuable opinions of the authors as under:

- (i) the main interest of the Library was centered on its collection of Persian manuscripts of Shia theology. But, the collection was poor on Indian history. Not a single old and authoritative text of any of the Persian documents relating to the Indo-Muslim period printed in the Bibliotheca India series of the Asiatic Society was found there;
- (ii) there were two copies of Abul Fazal's *Akbarnama* and *Ain-i-Akbari*, both complete and ardently transcribed in the very late 18th century: None of them could be considered as specimens of calligraphy, although some of the volumes were written in a clear legible hand;
- (iii) no historical letters and newspapers (Akhbarat) in the Persian language could be found in the collection, but there was a fragmentary letter-book of Aurangzeb's last years, consisting of notes from the emperor's dictation taken down by his secretary, Munshi Inayenthullah, for expansion into format Hassalhukns;
- (iv) two short collections of formal letters compiled by Munshis were also found there, but they were of no historical import, as they do not deal with any notable events, and
- (v) the Library was overcrowded with books (printed and lithographed) and manuscripts which in his opinion better be weeded out—such as textbooks of Madrashes, cheap lithographs of popular works of fiction, poetry, etc.

1.2 THE CATALOGUE

Manuscripts were wrongly entered in the catalogue prepared for the Nawab by an Arabic scholar from Egypt, who had very limited knowledge of Indo-Muslim history.

2 OBSERVATIONS

Establishment of a library by Nawab Nazim definitely indicates the influence of the culture of Muslim rulers of the Medieval India on him. But seeing the collection at the present and as was reported by Sir Sarkar, it could be safely remarked that Nawab Nazim and his descendents were not very much interested in building up a valuable collection. Otherwise, they would have collected valuable historical documents in the Persian language out of the loot of Delhi and Lucknow, as are found in the Rampur Raza Library (U P) and Khuda Baksh Library (Patna) collections. Poor collections on Shia theology and Indian history do not give us high idea about the then users of the Library. Moreover, Sir Sarkar did not point out any collection of Sanskrit, Pali and Bengali literature. Perhaps, the Nawabs were very much indifferent about these literatures. Sir

Sarkar had pointed out the fact that a major segment of the collection consisted of cheap lithographs of popular works (fiction, poetry, etc.) which could be picked up for a few annas in the Lucknow and Delhi bazars. Though the language of the lithographs was not stated, these popular works might be on Persian literature for the entertainment of the members of the royal family. It is worthwhile to note in this connection a curious fact mentioned by Sir Sarkar in his Report. He found two locked almirahs during both of his visits, which led him to presume that some mysterious manuscripts could be imprisoned in them. For this reason, he suggested that a well versed scholar in Shia teology be sent to explore the contents of these two almirahs. Although, the *Report* discussed at length about the quality of the collection, but it is silent on its exact quantity. According to an informed source[1], the Library contains more than three thousand manuscripts and seven thousand rare books in oriental languages as well as in English.

Muslims excelled in calligraphy, illustration and binding. These arts were their own, and none was their competitor. But, it has been rightly pointed out by Sarkar that none of the library's prized possessions could be considered as an example of high calligraphic standard.

Muslims did have bibliographic heritage and they imported even this in India, enabling compilation of many catalogues. It remained though in a crude form by our contemporary standards, nevertheless, served the purpose to tell the user what information is stored [4, p 65]. The *Report* mentioned that several mistakes in the catalogue entries of the Library were detected by Sarkar. The proof of this became visible to one of the authors of the present paper during his recent visit to the Library. He observed that Sir Sarkar himself had made several pencil corrections on the margin of the catalogue and put correct labels on the volumes concerned.

While royal libraries of this period can well be compared with their counterparts in contemporary West and even while it attracted scholars for study and research, the benefits from these rare collections, was really speaking, too limited. The level of its use was not commensurate with the cost it involved in maintenance and care. The Library of Nawab Nazim was no exception to this. Whether the Library's collection was accessible to persons other than the members of the royal family is difficult to determine, since, no such record could be evidenced.

3 CONCLUSION

The conclusion to this paper may be drawn by quoting the apt words of Dr S R Ranganathan, the father of Indian library science, in his radio talk in April 1956: "An account of the libraries in the first four periods (the Vedic, the Buddhistic, the Medieval, and the Muslim) must necessarily depend upon the historical research. This has not yet been done. The library profession is too

small in India to spare a person to fill up this antiquarian gap. Those trained in the scientific method of tracing history are too preoccupied with dynastic and political history to spare sufficient time for cultural history in general and library history in particular. "Sir Jadunath Sarkar, a historian and historiographer *per se*, was one of those few who could be considered as exceptions to the above. So was his *Report*, which is probably the first documentation on the Library of Nawab Nazim of Murshidabad.

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